

Crypto Currency Mining Facility Design and Implementation

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

A primer on the design considerations of constructing small, medium and large cryptocurrency mining operations as well as tertiary uses of byproducts generated.

2. Aim

To improve design concepts and reduce energy waste through the development of cryptocurrency mining operations.

3. Material and methods

Successful design and construction of 4 large scale mines between 2MW and 45MW, experience in development of prepackages mobile mining units. Utilizing experience spanning HVAC and electrical engineering design along with practical experience in automation and control programming.

4. Results

Determined appropriate airflow considerations and electrical equipment required to keep lowest cost operation while reducing energy consumption to bare minimum while also negating negative aspects such as wasted energy conversion.

5. Conclusions

This presentation effectively increases awareness to crypto-mining and blockchain supporting facilities in a responsible manner to reduce impact on surrounding industries as well as provide useful applications of heat energy generated.

6. Keywords

Cryptocurrency; Mining; Blockchain

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Author biography

Ray Bursey Ray has his Master's in Technology Management and a Post Graduate in Quality Management

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